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DESIGN OF POWER SiC TRANSISTOR EMBEDDED IN PCB SUPPORTED BY 3D SIMULATIONS

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Abstract *Thermo-mechanical simulation study of a power SiC transistor embedded in a printed circuit board (PCB) is presented. The analysis is focused on the optimization of the design in order to improve the thermal and mechanical reliability performance of the device. Numerical simulations are effectively used in the identification of critical areas in the systems using power transistors embedded in the PCB, and their optimization with respect to lower mechanical strain and better heat transfer, both leading to improved reliability of the final system.*

Keywords thermo-mechanical simulation, embedded power transistor, printed circuit board

1. INTRODUCTION

The recently developed technology of embedded die in a printed circuit board (PCB) eliminates wire bonds by replacing direct metallurgical contacts or soldering. This technology reduces parasitic inductance, capacitance and resistance of wire bonds and improves the electrical performance of the devices and systems. Moreover, the embedded packaging allows double sided cooling for power components [1, 2]. Mechanical stress invoked by thermal expansion and material fatigue is very important key factor for the reliability and long lifetime operation of power devices. During the development process of new technology, the numerical simulation is a powerful tool for design analysis, characterization, and optimization [3].

In this paper, we present a thermo-mechanical simulation study of a power SiC transistor embedded in PCB. Analyses demonstrate various thermal and mechanical stress behavior and properties at different geometry designs and operating conditions.

2. STRUCTURE AND MODEL DESCRIPTION

The device under investigation is SiC power MOSFET transistor embedded in PCB. The 3D model is depicted in Fig. 1. MOSFET semiconductor die is mounted to the copper lead frame. This structure is inserted into the double side PCB (FR4 material). Lamination and plating are used to create two additional routing copper layers on the top and bottom of the PCB. Particular layers are interconnected by vias and forms drain, source, and gate contacts. The thermal and mechanical properties of the materials for the simulation were taken from the default COMSOL library [4]. The heat source was

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placed on top of the SiC power transistor die, where heat is generated during operating conditions.

Fig. 1 3D model of embedded power SiC MOSFET for thermo-mechanical simulations.

3. SIMULATION RESULTS

The analysis of the embedded power MOSFET is focused on the influence of particular layers geometry on the thermal and mechanical stress properties and behavior. The investigated variables are vias diameter, vias thickness, vias distance, and lead frame size.

First, the impact of investigated variables on thermal properties was analyzed. Simulated time evolution of the thermal impedance Z_{th} of the embedded device is shown in Fig. 2. The device temperature is directly proportional to the thermal impedance. The higher thermal impedance means higher device temperature. From the simulations, higher vias diameter and lead frame size decrease the device thermal impedance mainly at times from 1×10^{-1} s up to steady state due to higher thermal conductivity of the heat sink from SiC die through the higher area. The higher vias distance slightly increases the thermal impedance in the range around time 1×10^{-3} s. The higher vias distance leads to a lower thermal capacity of the vias. The impact of vias thickness on thermal impedance is almost negligible.

After thermal analysis of the device, the mechanical stress induced by thermal expansion was investigated. The mechanical stress was analyzed at three different times 1×10^{-3} s, 1×10^{-1} s, and steady state operating condition (DC). The mechanical stress was analyzed

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at vias where delamination or rupture can occur. Fig. 3 shows mechanical von Mises stress in the vias for different vias diameter, vias thickness, vias distance, and lead frame size.

Fig. 2 Simulated thermal impedance Z_{th} of the device at different investigated geometry variables.

Fig. 3 Mechanical stress in the vias at different investigated geometry variables for various pulse times.

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Although the thermal impedance and related structure temperature is slightly lower, the mechanical stress increases for the higher via diameter. It is caused by more robust and less flexible vias with higher diameter. Despite the slightly higher thermal impedance and temperature with higher vias thickness for pulse time of 1×10^{-1} s and steady state, the mechanical stress is better distributed in the vias and decreases. Vias distance has no impact on the mechanical stress for times 1×10^{-1} s, and steady state. As the vias distance increases, the mechanical stress is slightly higher for times of 1×10^{-3} s. It is directly proportional to the change of the thermal impedance and temperature only around the time of 1×10^{-3} s. The significant reduction of the thermal impedance and temperature with larger lead frame size decreases the mechanical stress in the vias for time of 1×10^{-3} s and steady state condition.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Presented thermo-mechanical simulation study of SiC power transistor embedded in PCB reveal significant influence of the geometry design on thermal and mechanical stress of power transistor embedded in PCB. It shows that mainly higher lead frame size leads to lower device temperature and mechanical stresses. Since the mechanical stress in the device layers and interfaces proportionally degrades the device reliability, lower mechanical stress prolongs lifetime at a steady state and especially during cycling, pulse operating conditions.

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